

Roles in User Experience Design - Transferring insights from experience oriented disciplines

Simon Kremer¹
simon.kremer@pe.mw.tum.de

Stefan Günther¹
stefan.guenther@mytum.de

Udo Lindemann¹
udo.lindemann@pe.mw.um.de

¹*Technical University of Munich, Germany*

Abstract User Experience Design (UXD) incorporates the increasing importance of emotional aspects in user product interaction and aims at creating holistic experiences. In UXD teams, members with various competences and tasks have to collaborate towards a common experience goal. Roles define which tasks and competences are required. Linking requirements from traditional product development and UXD, we defined an UXD role model in a previous project. Nevertheless, UXD is a rather young discipline within product development. But creating experiences is a traditional focus of other disciplines outside engineering design. We aim at transferring knowledge from those disciplines to support the design of fascinating User Experience. We identified relevant experience disciplines and selected the four most promising ones for our analysis: game development, film production, tourism and marketing. Based on an interview study we analyzed a broad range of roles. We joined the main insights into the existing UXD role model – confirming and enriching existing roles and introducing the new role of an Experience Author. Our approach widens the scope of experience designers and supports product development teams by providing required roles on the way to User Experience.

Keywords *User experience, Design processes, Emotional design, Interdisciplinary teams, Team roles*

Introduction

Besides traditional aspects like functionality and usability, User Experience (UX) widens the scope towards the questions: How is a user experiencing a product? What is the user experiencing with the product? This requires a holistic analysis and design of users' expectation, cognition and assessment of technical products (Roto et al, 2011). The aim of User Experience Design (UXD) are exciting interactions and enjoyable stories with products to create emotional customer loyalty – by triggering emotions of the user (Norman, 2005) and satisfying customer needs (Kim et al., 2011). In UXD, members from various disciplines have to collaborate towards a common UX goal. Therefore, it is relevant to define roles which shape UX teams and which have to be fulfilled by people in product development projects.

Figure 1 presents our research approach, aiming at the goal: enhanced roles for User Experience Design. The left side of the figure explains previous work which we use as starting point: In an interdisciplinary research project with automotive industry we analyzed specific requirements of User Experience Design and characteristics of product development processes. Based on theoretical UX background and conditions in real development projects, we joined both point of views into an UXD process (www.designingexperiences.org, Bengler et al. 2014). The roles included in the process summarize and specify tasks and competences of relevant UXD disciplines on

the way to User Experience. The UX roles focus on insights from areas like engineering design, industrial design, interaction design, etc.

Yet, development teams coming out of these fields are not used to focus on designing experiences. On the other hand, disciplines like tourism, marketing, gaming and film industry traditionally concentrate on creating experiences and fascinating their "users". Therefore, we see a great potential for learning from these areas when designing the User Experience with technical products. We have already analyzed important triggers for the emergence of experiences in these disciplines (e.g. challenge, surprise, atmosphere,...) and transferred the experience factors to UXD (Kremer et al. 2015). In this paper we investigate which roles take part in design processes in the experience oriented disciplines (right side of Figure 1).

By building on existing work concerning relevant roles for UXD and analyzing team compositions and established roles in experience focused disciplines, we work towards our goal: extract new role aspects to be introduced when implementing UXD in industrial practice. Accordingly, it is important to analyze the following questions: Which aspects out of analyzed disciplines emphasize characteristics of existing UXD roles? Which aspects of experience oriented disciplines expand characteristics of existing UXD roles? Which new roles can we introduce to broaden

Figure 1. Research Approach.

the scope of UX teams?

User Experience background

This section presents content of the left side of Figure 1. Concerning our goal, we firstly sum up disciplines involved in UXD. After defining our understanding of a role we present the existing User Experience role model as starting point for our approach.

Disciplines in User Experience Design

User Experience Design – due to its holistic approach – is influenced by a broad range of disciplines (Gube, 2010). Approaches range from psychological to economic and from quality oriented to value oriented points of view (Roto et al., 2010). Hekkert & Schifferstein (2007) categorized disciplines which surround the field of User Experience (see Figure 2). According to the subjective characteristic of experiences, psychology plays a major role. User Experience Design combines the sub disciplines concerning perception, cognition and emotion. Between, further disciplines complement the interplay – either with social and behavioral background (e.g. psychological aesthetics), technical background (mechanical engineering) or customer centered (e.g. human computer interaction). This interdisciplinary field offers a potential for creating versatile User Experiences. But at the same time, different theoretical basics and goals often hinder collaboration. Therefore UXD should not focus on a specific interpretation of experiences, but rather coordinate involved disciplines. Instead of interpreting UXD as a new discipline, we can see it as an overarching link and management function (Saffer, 2008).

Role definition

The highlighted challenges do not only concern theory of UXD. In industrial practice of product development UXD is performed by people coming out of the described disciplines. As mentioned before, coordinating input and duties from various disciplines is the major challenge. Therefore, it is important to define roles which are necessary when designing User Experience. These roles should guide UX team members and enable realization of a common experience goal. As a starting point, we briefly specify

our understanding of a role, before introducing the existing UX roles.

“A role is a bunch of expectations, which evolve out of social processes” (Bergmann & Daub, 2008). We do not focus on social characteristics (e.g. Belbin, 2010) but rather on job-oriented expectations of team roles (Wagner & Patzak, 2015). Accordingly, three aspects define a role: environment, tasks and competences. Figure 3 illustrates these aspects of a role based on the example of a crane operator.

The **environment** describes the subject of work. Wagner & Patzak (2015) name it as “purpose of the role”. Mostly the associated discipline provides this information. In the example of Figure 3, the construction site represents the environment for all construction workers. Consequently, the purpose of the role is contributing to finish the construction, for example building a house.

Figure 2. Disciplines involved in User Experience Design (according to Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2007).

Figure 3. Aspects of a role: environment, tasks and competences.

The **tasks** of a role are the main contributions to the work progress. Wagner & Patzak (2015) combine “tasks, duties and responsibilities” as one aspect of a role characterization, as given task comes with the responsibility of accomplishing it in the correct way. The crane operator’s task is to safely control the crane.

The **competences** contain personal characteristics and skills. Wagner & Patzak (2015) describe these as “behavior expectation” and job-related “competences”. Both are necessary to fulfill the requirements of a role and to process the allocated tasks. E.g. a crane operator has knowledge about technical characteristics and physical behavior of the crane. Accordingly, he is expected to anticipate its movement.

Existing roles in User Experience Design

As described before, working multi-disciplinary is a crucial characteristic of User Experience Design. Roles can help structuring and managing the various fields involved in practice. This section explains the existing roles in UXD which we build our approach on. Human centered design requires the involvement of the following product development roles (ISO, 1999): application domain specialist, business analyst; systems analyst, systems engineer, programmer; marketer, salesperson; user interface designer, visual

designer; human factors and ergonomics expert, HCI specialist; technical author, trainer and support personnel. UXD is located within human centered design. Therefore, it is necessary to build on the mentioned roles but specify them according to UX characteristics. In a previous research project with automobile industry we faced this challenge. Designing a complex product such as a car requires collaboration among multiple participants, representing different departments within the company. Often, each of these individuals has to satisfy different technical and regulatory requirements. Therefore, we defined relevant roles as part of a User Experience Design process: www.designingexperiences.org (Bengler et al., 2014).

Figure 4 introduces the five UXD roles according to designingexperiences.org. Table 1 exemplarily presents the full description of the Experience Designer; followed by brief descriptions for the four other roles.

- *The Human Factors Expert analyzes and evaluates the User Experience with appropriate methods and tools and reveals potentials from the user’s point of view.*
- *The Developer is up to date concerning technologies, develops and integrates concepts*

Figure 4. Roles in the User Experience Design process (www.designingexperiences.org).

and implements the story into the technical product.

- The **Storykeeper** directs the project to maintain the story, monitors requirements, guides as a consultant and represents the project to management.
- The **Customer Expert** has customer insights and knowledge about the global market, quantifies customer motives and communicates the User Experience

A detailed description of all roles is available online. Different sub roles specify each role with tasks and com-petences, as shown in Table 1 on the example of the Experience Designer. The original online description lists tasks and competences but does not clearly separate them. According to our definition of a role, we sep-arated the role description into these two aspects, which is a change to the original appearance. The general environment is the field of product development. Summing up, roles are not representing certain positions in a company, but competences and tasks which are necessary for certain development steps in the Experience Design process. The UXD roles represent the members of an Experience Design team. We use these roles as foundation. In order to define enhanced, holistic roles for experience creation, we revise them by including insights from experience oriented disciplines (see Figure 1).

Research approach: analyzing experience oriented disciplines

We examined disciplines that focus on creating experiences to enhance roles for User Experience Design. When having analyzed most valuable experience factors in other disciplines in a previous study, we worked out criteria to extract the most promising disciplines (Kremer et al., 2015). For our present work we revised these criteria and came up with the following criteria to select relevant disciplines out of the identified experi-ence areas: sports, adventure events, shopping events, gastronomy, concerts, tourism, marketing, gaming and film production.

- **Know-how:** *The discipline should systematically develop experiences for people based on a design process, driven by several roles. This excludes random occurrences of experiences.*
- **Commercial benefit:** *In general, people should be willing to pay for the experiences and the producer should aim at profit by selling the*

experiences.

- **Popularity:** *Most people should already have had an experience in the field.*
- **Availability:** *The discipline should provide access for collecting data through interviews. This involves reach-ing contact persons and their willingness to take time for an interview.*

According to these criteria we rejected several disciplines (e.g. gastronomy due to availability concerns). The four selected disciplines are: **tourism, marketing, gaming and film production**. We chose semi-structured interviews as method to collect data from the professional practice, because we wanted to use the advantage of getting direct in-depth information from experts. The interview guideline consisted of three major parts:

- *What is an experience from your (organizational) point of view? What are the experience factors?*
- *How is the user's experience planned and developed?*
- *Which roles are involved in the experience development? And what are their tasks and competences?*

The organizations for our interviews we found through an online search. The search terms consisted of an alternation of the word “experience” connected with a discipline-related word – e.g. “adventure travel”. We performed in-depth interviews with employees from 14 organizations. These interviews resulted in a list of experience factors for each discipline (roles’ environment) and role descriptions (specified into tasks and competences). We confirmed the information about the roles through the description of the German federal employment agency, where we could find a brief description of each role from one comparable source. For promising roles we performed a further literature research. To extract common findings, we merged similar characterized roles in each discipline. Nevertheless, it was crucial to keep the original role descriptions in focus. In this way, we ensured a balance between summarizing general findings and enabling transfer them to UXD on the one hand as well as keeping valuable original information on the other hand.

In a further step we compared the extracted roles with the existing UXD roles described before. The comparison focused on the role characterization: tasks, competences and environment. The result of this

Table 1. Experience Designer (according to www.designingexperiences.org)

Experience Designer	Tasks	Competences
		Creative Person
	...contributes creative ideas	...can think laterally and cross borders
		Storyteller
	...creates story and storyboard.	...has a creative and psychological understanding, ...can convey ideas, ...is able to tell stories.
		Experience Designer
	...translates story into concepts.	...has a comprehensive approach for implementing the concept.

research is adding value to the existing model – by new roles, adjusting roles and confirming roles.

Results

In this section we describe the results of our approach. Starting with factors which shape experiences in each specific discipline, we present discipline specific roles and the enhanced roles for UXD.

Experience factors: the roles' environment

The experience factors form the environment of the roles in each discipline. Table 2 lists the factors discipline wise – providing the goals for experience designers in the different professional fields. They are a collocation from the interviews and examination of the “products” of each discipline (e.g. touristic offer, advertisement, online game and movie).

While a deep understanding of the user and triggers for experiences is required in all discipline, there are differences concerning the specific characteristics of experiences. For example in tourism experiences are mostly created by exceptional and unknown/new situations. This is comparable to extraordinary User Experience which emerges out of special or memorable events with products according to Schifferstein & Hekkert (2008). An exemplary tourist offer could be a mountain tour to climb Mount Kilimanjaro. To most people this journey would be an experience and could meet several named factors. To someone, who has not been in Tanzania, it is a new country, new culture, and a magnificent nature and the encounter of people plays a big role when climbing the mountain with the local folks. At the same time the ascent is a tough mountaineering expedition and borderline experience. The daily routine of experience designers in tourism is creating newness and designing a program with memorable situations.

In contrast to this, gaming industry does not focus on singular but on continuous experiences – e.g. by

providing long lasting fun, sensual appeal and challenge. In marketing and film production, experience designers have to design a coherent marketing concept or film structure which allows the visitor to project himself into the story

Experience creating roles of each discipline

Table 3 presents an overview of the roles which we extracted from the interviews – separated into four different categories of roles (first column). The first row shows an Author/Story supplier. This role supplies the story at the start of the design process. The roles in the second category characterize a kind of designer. These roles adapt the original story to fit to the product. Category 3 specifies a developer or implementer. These roles implement the adapted story of the final product and have the required background knowledge. The last row 4 shows managing roles. They are located at a higher level of the development team and have to make main decisions concerning the experience creating process.

Table 3 contains only the role names. Each role consists of certain tasks and competences, as introduced before. We present the unique characterizations of the roles as part of the enhanced UXD role model in the next section. Two roles caught our special interest and seem to have a high potential to bring up new aspects for UXD: the **director** and the **author**. The author brings in a totally new starting point and access for designing a User Experience. The director combines artistic and organizing aspects – showing accordance to several roles from designingexperiences.org (see Table 6). Table 4 and 5 present complete role descriptions of director and author – information from the interviews extended with details from a literature research.

Enhanced role model for User Experience Design

Table 6 presents our main result: the enhanced role model for UXD. It is based on the UX roles from designingexperiences.org. The table contains three

Table 2. Experience factors of the four analyzed disciplines.

Tourism	Marketing	Game development	Film production
unknown countries & cultures	emotional attachment	fun and excitement	coherent film structure
encounters with people	memories	appealing design	artistic appeal
borderline experiences – mountain tour / expedition	comprehensive stories	community	emotional attachment
magnificent nature	sense of community	affinity to game content	self-projection of the spectator
fulfillment of dreams		challenge	

Table 3. Experience creating roles in each discipline.

	Tourism	Marketing	Game development	Film production
1		Story supplier	Author	Author
2	Mountain guide	User	Game Designer	Director
	Person on site	Psychologist	Test group	Test group
3	Geography specialist	Task-related developer	Technical implementer	Actors
	Product manager			Cutter
4	Tourism expert	Experienced developer	Editor	Productions manager

main columns: the **name** of the role, the **characteristic** of each sub-role separated into tasks and competences and the analysis **insights from other disciplines**. The new role model consists of six roles. Each role is divided into further sub-roles. Because of limited space we only describe new and adjusted roles and just name confirmed exiting roles in the two left columns. The original role descriptions are available online. The blue phrases highlight the new information, which we transferred to UXD. In the right column, we display the original role description. It is blue if it is new information and black if the content presents confirmed details of existing roles.

The major change to the pre-existing roles is the added Experience Author which we mainly derived from game and film author. This change should lead to **more engaging experience stories for the user**. Further adjustments are the enhancement of the Human Factors Expert and the Experience Designer. The novel aspects of the Human Factors Expert originate in the mountain guide in tourism, which should allow fitting the product with its **story more closely to the user's demand**. Insights from the Person on site in tourism and from the psychologist in marketing enhance the Experience Designer. This change should help to **integrate influencing context factors upon an experience** into the design process. In the following we present details of the three mentioned improvements.

The **Experience Author** is changing the initial development situation. He provides an engaging and inspirational product story at the beginning of the design process. The story is the basis for the further development. This might lead to a stronger User Experience. In the original experience disciplines the author provides a comprehensive story at the beginning of the process. It is an overarching story which provides the framework for detailed subsequent experience story design. Knudsen (2016) describes this process for film production: "The vision of the screenplay will then be shaped by the careful selection of director, cinematographer, editor and so on, and what eventually ends up on the screen may or may not live up to the original vision of the screenwriter." In

Table 4. Characterization of the Director: [1] StoryCrate: Tabletop Storyboarding for Live Film Production (2012); [2] Novel Management Model to Increase Visual Effect Productivity (2013); [3] Moving Cameras and Living Movies (2013); [4] The Film Director Prepares: A Complete Guide to Directing for Film and TV (2010).

Director	
Tasks	Competences
...designs the artistic result,	...requires patience, creativity
...works with the cutter on final edit [1],	and an inner visual skill – like an instinct or intuition,
...makes the principal creative decisions during the filming process [1],	leading abilities, differentiation between being forceful and letting things happen [4].
...designs the camera angels [1],	...is organized and structured [1], [3], [4].
...specifies visual effect details [2] / creates physical, visual appearance [3],	
...decides the set of actors.	

our role model the Storykeeper pays attention to maintaining the initial vision of the author. Concluding, the new role of the Experience Author is not changing the User Experience Design process but rather provides another access possibility to start into the process.

We added an Influence Expert as sub-role of the **Experience Designer**. This new sub-role we derived from the person on site in tourism and from the psychologist in marketing. In both cases they have real insights about what context factors influence the User Experience. So far the Human Factors Expert evaluates the User Experience in the UXD process. Whereas he focuses on the user's point of view, the Influence Expert reveals impacts of environmental influences (e.g. culture, physical environment,...) upon the user and his ex-perience with the product. This stresses the importance of the surrounding/context which shapes the setting of product use. Thus, the Experience Designer unites both analysis and design of the intended UX based on his psychological understanding.

The **Human Factors Expert** has the sub-role Analysis Specialist. We extended this sub-role by the task to monitor the user while using the product to gain implicit information about the usage. This specialty we ex-tracted from the mountain guide in tourism. He accompanies the hikers on the mountain and can gain specific user feedback. In contrast to the Influence Expert he rather focuses on the user than on the context of usage. Another specific aspect of the mountain guide his possibility to influence the User Experience during the actual time of usage. This brings up an advanced way of creating experiences for a user. It allows reaction to the user's desires and refining the User Experience during usage. Accompanying a user in real usage situations will reveal new information about the usage and will go beyond questionnaires or traditional test group observations. In order to introduce this knowledge into the development process, the Human Factors Expert needs to be very sensitive and a good observer when accompanying the user.

Table 5. Characterization of the Author: [5] Screenwriting and emotional rhythm (2014); [6] The Total Filmmaker: Thinking of screenwriting, directing and editing as one role (2016); [7] ScriptEase: A generative/adaptive programming paradigm for game scripting (2007); [8] Player as Author: conjecturing online game creation modalities and infrastructure (2005).

Author	
Tasks	Competences
...has the idea,	...has expertise in creating and detailing storylines and all the intricacies [7],
...writes an inspiring and engaging story,	...has strengths in the creative process [7],
...creates an order of things, sequence of images, words and sounds that produce a flow of feelings [5],	...has narrative mindset [8],
...creates a living story that excites and moves the creator [6].	...has cinematographic mindset and focuses on visual language and aesthetics as a primary form of communication and involvement [8].

Exemplary development situation

In the following, we highlight our enhanced role model for UXD with an exemplary development situation. The description focuses on the tasks of each role.

Nevertheless, the development process is based on strong co-operation between the roles.

The initial situation is the development of a product, with focus on User Experience. The UXD starts with the search for the best underlying experience oriented story. Therefore the **Experience Author creates an en-gaging and inspirational story with and around**

the product and the user. The following development phases build on this initial story. The Customer Expert now defines the user group and the as-is situation of product usage. Customer Expert, Experience Designer and Developer create the framework for the project, compile user profiles and generate first concept ideas. These aspects influence the subsequent elaboration. In a further step, the UXD team integrates different concepts into the overarching story and the Human Factors Expert evaluates the impact of the story with the help of questionnaires or interviews. **Implicit usage information gathered from real life**

Table 6. Roles for the UXD with new inputs from four experience oriented disciplines.

The role	Tasks of the role in the UXD process	Competences of	Original role in the other discipline
Human Factors Expert	Analysis Specialist		Tourism: Mountain guide: — always accompanies the users during time of usage — knows the environment of product usage — can influence the user's experience at the time of usage
	...accompanies the user to gain implicit usage information.	...is sensitive and a good observer.	Game development and film production: Test group: — tests the product — values the level of experience
Experience Designer	UX-Evaluation Expert		
	Creative Person		Game development: Game designer: — creates the design of the game — supplies the story line
	Storyteller		Film production: Director: — creates a storyboard/prompt book — decides about the scenes — is responsible for the artistic success — works with the cutter on the final edit — defines the visual identity — has an inner visual skill to create a story flow
	Experience Designer		Tourism: Person on site: — lives in the environment of product use — has continuous contact with the user — contributes this knowledge to product development
Storykeeper	Influence Expert		Marketing: Psychologist: — knows the influences to a user's experience — considers the impact of correlations of product details
	...contributes first-hand knowledge.	...knows the environment, in which the product is used, ...knows the influence factors on a User Experience.	
	Project Controller		Tourism: Tourism expert: — has last decision from business side — knows the market
	Requirement Manager		Game development: Game editor: — knows target group and market — checks the game consistence
Storykeeper	Project Manager		Product manager: — plans strategies for the product design
	Consultant		Film production: Producer: — controls the technical and economic success — makes decisions Editor: — makes decisions about the content and the adequate form of the film

(part 1)

The role	Tasks	Competences of	Original role in the other discipline
Developer	the role in the UXD process		
	Technology-Scout		Tourism: Geography specialist: — knows the possibilities based on the landscape — Product manager: — introduces background knowledge about the touristic area
	Concept Engineer		Marketing: Task related developer: — has specialized knowledge — creates the visceral appearance of the product Game development: Game designer: — designs the game content
	Requirement Developer		Illustrator: — creates games through models and drawings — creates prototypes Film production: Cutter: — processes the final touch through a technical expertise (incl. technical and artistic aspects) — has close relationship with the Director (cf. Experience Designer) Director: — decides about the set of actors
Customer Expert	Customer and Market Expert		Game development: Game editor: — knows the target group and the market
	Statistician		Tourism: Tourism expert: — is market specialist and knows the discipline
	Communication Expert		Mountain guide: — collects insights from the customer
Experience Author	Storysupplier		Marketing: Story supplier: — has a precise imagination for the concept — supplies the basis for the following development Game development: Game author or inventor: — introduces the story, which is the initial situation for the development — can be a professional inventor, or anyone with an idea Creative director: — has a vision for the game, including a auditory and visual identity Film production: Author: — creates the base for the production — is a creative idea provider — works together with the Producer
	...develops the complete storyline for the following development, ...documents and communicates the whole story for the development team.	...can be a professional developer or any idea creator, ...is not a fixed member of the team.	

(Table 6 part 2)

observations supports fully aiming on an experience for the user group. Thereafter, Experience Designer, Customer Expert and Developer develop the story further to a storyboard, which gives detailed information about the entire interaction of user and product. At this step the **Experience Designer ensures the intended User Experience with his knowledge about environmental influencing factors.** The Storykeeper looks out for maintaining the vision of the Experience Author's initial story along the total process, to ensure that the inspirational aspects do not get lost while translating them into a physical product subsequently. The Developer designs the product components, while the Human Factors

Experts evaluates the actual User Experience. The Customer Expert communicates the underlying story, highlights UX-potentials and creates a feeling of anticipation. Throughout the development process, the Storykeeper screens the achievement of UX milestones (Kremer et al, 2014).

Discussion

We chose interviews for collecting our information. This is due to the fact that we wanted to gather knowledge directly from experts in experience oriented disciplines. To get reliable results we contacted several experts in each discipline. A further advantage of interviews was the chance of asking

further questions. This gave us the possibility to get answers of the same expert regarding: the experience factors, the involved roles in the experience creation process and the roles' tasks and competences. We confirmed our results through literature – focusing on the author and the director. Our study revealed promising exemplary insights from experience oriented disciplines. The fact that most insights confirmed the existing UXD roles of designingexperiences.org supports direction of the initial role model. Nevertheless, further literature review and analysis of sources and disciplines outside the scope of this study might lead to novel findings – confirming the found roles but uncovering new roles as well.

The main new role which we transferred to UXD is the Experience Author. The high value of this role is the enthusiastic story for the product. But attention has to be paid not to change the actual UXD process. The other team members might not accept the story. For that reason, the team and especially the Experience Designer is processing the given story in further steps.

Furthermore, the mountain guide has a unique possibility to create or influence the User Experience during usage. He can interact with the user during the experience. There are first technical ways of implementing this feature – e.g. voice instructions in the car, on a smart phone or on other devices. In addition, we placed the task to record implicit information about the usage as an adjustment of the Human Factors Expert. He accompanies the user during product use to gain implicit information about the user's behaviour. A technical device could as well implement this task – by tracking and analysing usage data.

Summary and outlook

User Experience Design widens the scope of product development beyond traditional functional and pragmatic aspects and aims at fascinating experiences. Accordingly, people fulfilling various UXD roles have to collaborate together. We consider a role as a collection of certain tasks and competences located in a specific environment. A UXD role model out of a previous project links requirements from traditional product development and UXD and served as basis for our approach. As other disciplines are ahead of product development concerning the design of experiences we aimed at enhancing existing UXD roles with insights from those disciplines. Therefore, we identified relevant experience disciplines and selected those, which were most promising for our study: game development, film production, tourism and marketing. In those selected disciplines we performed an interview study and extracted relevant roles for creating experiences (e.g. person on site in tourism, story supplier in marketing, author in gaming and director in film production). Each analyzed role reveals possible competences and tasks for designing experiences and can inspire UXD teams. Analyzing and comparing all roles throughout the different disciplines, we gathered various relevant UX tasks. We integrated our findings into the existing UX role model. Our analysis generally confirmed the pre-

existing roles. As additional main role we introduced the Experience Author who acts as story supplier and visionary towards a holistic product experience. Furthermore, we enriched existing roles: The Experience Designer should also perform as an Influence Expert – having deep insights of the real world usage environment and continuous contact with the user. The Human Factors Expert should (similar to a mountain guide in tourism) accompany the users during time of usage and should be able to influence the User Experience at the time of usage

Our model is a first step towards transferring the gathered approaches to product development. We paid attention to “translating” discipline specific insights to product design but on the other hand providing links to the original experience discipline and not losing exceptional role characteristics. From this starting point, future work will focus on validating and advancing new found UX role aspects – investigating relevant literature which aims at identified potentials and integrating further disciplines in our research. Using design thinking approaches, we want to engage with and learn from people committed to relevant disciplines.

References

- Bartindale, T., Sheikh, A., Taylor, N., Wright, P., Olivier, P. (2012). *StoryCrate: Tabletop Storyboarding for Live Film Production*. New York: ACM
- Belbin, M. (2010). *Team Roles at Work*. Oxford, Elsevier.
- Bengler, K., Butz, A., Diwischek, L., Frenkler, F., Körber, M., Kremer, S., Landau, M., Loehmann, S., Lindemann, U., Michailidou, I., Norman, D., Pfalz, F., von Saucken, C., Schumann, J. (2014). *CAR@TUM: The Road to User Experience*. www.designingexperiences.org
- Bergmann, G., Daub, J. (2008). *Systemisches-, Innovations- und Kompetenzmanagement (Vol. 2)*. Wiesbaden: Gabler.
- Cutumisu, M., Onuczko, C., McNaughton, M., Roy, T., Schaeffer, J., Schumacher, A., Siegel, J., Szafron, D., Waugh, K., Carbonaro, M., Duff, H., Gillis, S. (2007). *ScriptEase: A generative/adaptive programming paradigm for game scripting*. Oxford: Elsevier
- David, I. (2014). *Screenwriting and Emotional Rhythm*. Bristol: Intellect
- Esomba, S. (2013). *Moving Cameras and Living Movies*. Raleigh: Lulu
- Gube, J. (2010). What is user experience design? Overview, tools and resources, *Smashing Magazine*, <http://uxdesign.smashingmagazine.com/2010/10/05/what-is-user-experience-design-overview-tools-and-resources/>
- Hekkert, P; Schifferstein, H. (2007). *Product Experience*. San Diego: Elsevier.

Kim, J., Park, S., Hassenzahl, M., Eckoldt, K. (2011). *The Essence of Enjoyable Experiences: The Human Needs – A Psychological Needs-Driven Experience Design Approach*. Springer, Orlando.

Knudsen, E. (2016). *The Total Filmmaker: Thinking of screenwriting, directing and editing as one role*. Milton Park: Taylor & Francis

Kremer, S., Michailidou, I., Saucken, C. v. and Lindemann, U. (2014). *User Experience Milestones - Structuring the Development of Experience Products. Design, User Experience, and Usability. Theories, Methods, and Tools for Designing the User Experience*. Springer: 308-318.

Kremer, S., Hoffmann, A., Lindemann, U. (2015). Transferring Approaches from Experience Oriented Disciplines to User Experience Design: The ExoUX Model. iasdr 2015 interplay, Proceedings, International Association of Societies of Design Research (IASDR), 2015, 1163-1175.

Norman, D. (2005). *Emotional Design why we love (or hate) everyday things*. New York: Basic Books

Roto, V.; Law, E; Vermeeren, A.; Hoonhout, J. (2011). *User experience white paper - Bringing clarity to the concept of user experience*. <http://www.allaboutux.org/files/UX-WhitePaper.pdf>

Saffer, D. (2008): *The disciplines of user experience*. San Francisco, CA: Kicker Studio.

Schreibman, M. (2010). *The Film Director Prepares: A Complete Guide to Directing for Film and TV*. New York: Lone Eagle

Tavares, J., Gil, R., Roque, L. (2005). *Player as Author: conjecturing online game creation modalities and infrastructure*. Vancouver: DIGRA

Wagner, K. W., Patzak, G. (2015). *Performance Excellence - Der Praxisleitfaden zum effektiven Prozessmanagement*. München: Hanser.

Yothino, M., Rueangsirasak, W., Chaisricharoen, R. (2013). *Novel Management Model to Increase Visual Effect Productivity*. Surat Thani: ISCIT